

Effects of Jigsaw (iv) Instructional Strategy on Performance in Concept Electromagnetism among Secondary School Students in Gusau Metropolis.

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Abstract

The teaching strategy adopted by teachers during teaching could be a determinant of their achievement on students' academic performance. Therefore, the study investigated the effects of Jigsaw IV Instructional Strategy (J4IS) on academic performance in concept of electromagnetism by secondary school physics students in Government Senior Secondary Schools Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State. The objectives of the study were to examine the mean difference in the performance of students taught concepts of electromagnetism with J4IS and the influence of gender on effectiveness of the strategy. Two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. A quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) 2023/2024 academic session physics students in Government Secondary Schools in Gusau metropolis. A simple random sampling technique was employed to select 4 senior secondary schools. The sample size for the study was 105 students. Test retest method was employed to determine the reliability coefficient using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and found to be 0.77. The content validity of the test items was done by 3 experts from physics department and test and measurements in Federal University Gusau. Research Questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics of T-test at 0.05 level of significance. The research findings revealed that students taught with J4IS performed better and also male and female students performed equally when taught with J4IS. It was recommended among others, training should be organized by the State Ministry of Education on the use of J4IS for Senior Secondary Schools physics teaching and learning in the state.

Keywords: Jigsaw IV, Strategy, Academic, Performance, Physics.

Introduction

Physics as a scientific discipline holds significance across various technological and national development domains. It is also a prerequisite for numerous specialized science and engineering courses in universities and tertiary institutions. For a developing country like Nigeria a robust physics education is imperative to foster growth. Various researchers have offered distinctive on physics. Servey and Jewett (2004) defined physics as a foundational physical science that delves into the fundamental principles governing the universe serving as the bedrock for other scientific disciplines. The Sci-Tech Encyclopedia (2012) characterizes physics as a collective realm responsible for elucidating all observable natural phenomena.

Adolphus, Ekineh and Aderonmu (2021) highlighted that certain studies have identified prevalent use of traditional teacher-centered approaches in classroom interactions among science teachers predominant employ teacher-centered methods

such as lectures and discussions. Mehmood and Rehman (2011) similarly found parallels in Pakistan's teaching and classroom interactions, echoing the situation in Nigeria. Their findings depict a sequential process involving teachers: introducing a brief content summary, utilizing audiovisual aids to enhance student comprehension, delivering lectures at a pace allowing students to take note, assessing teaching effectiveness through post-session questions and assigning and reviewing homework. This approach portrays students as passive recipients of information while the teacher assumes the role of sole provider of knowledge.

According to Isa & Muhammad (2019) students that are not active in the process of acquiring knowledge are less motivated. The instructional methods use by teachers play a vital role in passing down knowledge and as well in meaningful learning. However, the use of lecture method by teachers is facing serious criticisms because it is of advantage to only active and hardworking students. This situation has pushed researchers in Education and more specifically Science Education to look for a more convenient ways for science students to be engaged with meaningful interaction in a classroom setting. Isa & Muhammad (2019) stated that many teaching methods and more importantly students centered approaches have been advocated for use in classroom for meaningful learning. Cooperative Learning Strategy was widely used among others. Gillies & Boyle (2010) posited that cooperative learning is an instructional practice which improves students' academic performance and socialization. However, many teachers cannot properly implement it in their classrooms (Banani & Aman (2022). Cooperative learning gives room for students' critical thinking, answering of questions, sharing opinions as well increases both students and teacher's learning activities in teaching even when exposed to online learning and one of the key instructional strategies that enhance creative thinking (Navarro-Pablo & Gallardo-Saborido (2015) & Gonzalez et al 2020)

According to Gök and Sylay (2010), cooperative group problem solving is utilized because it is useful for sharing problem-solving techniques among groups and is an excellent way to teach complicated skills. It also simplifies complex problems. To explain cooperative learning, academics have put forth a number of theories. According to Johnson (2003), the social interdependence theory is a framework for goal-setting that establishes how people interact and ultimately shapes the outcomes for groups. The collaborative technique gives students the chance to share their own original ideas, interact with classmates, and impart scientific information (Zakariyya, 2014). It restricts the notion of a teacher-oriented educational approach in which students absorb teachers' expertise through traditional method. This encourages individual learner to be industrious and self-confident. The teaching approach is known as "problem driven learning," which starts with a problem that has to be addressed and is presented in a way that requires pupils to learn new information in order to solve it. In collaborative learning, students cooperate to solve problems and finish assignments. According to Laal, et al. (2014), collaborative teaching is any situation in which two or more individuals try to understand a concept jointly, especially when it comes to working together as a group to solve problems.

More importantly, J4IS enables teachers to introduce materials, administer expert group quizzes, conduct a review process before individual assessments, and only re-teach information that was not sufficiently covered in the first collaborative group projects (Josiah & Manlikik, 2021). The J4IS seeks to improve positive educational outcomes and lessen learning conflict through the use of Jigsaw workouts. It's a group-based teaching approach where students are arranged into "home" or "jigsaw" groups inside a class. After that, the students in the jigsaw groups are rearranged into "expert" groups, which are made up of one member from each jigsaw group. Following instruction on the work, every student returns to their jigsaw group to make a contribution. Students can be taught both the theoretical and practical parts of physics using this teaching design. A good teaching strategy related to constructivism is the Jigsaw IV Instructional Strategy (J4IS). This is due to the fact that with J4IS students engage in peer interaction, exchanging personal experiences related to a particular Physics subject to build their own knowledge. In addition, each student makes a unique contribution to the construction of knowledge by conjecturing about any physics job or topic that needs to be solved. They assess the strategy's viability as well, and when they are able to do so, they make an effort to provide the right responses to assignments. Likewise using the approach to understand topics raises students' performance.

Gender matters immensely when it comes to teaching and studying physics. According to Okoro (2011), gender and students' performance in science might be impacted by the method of instruction employed in the classroom. He emphasized that when the cooperative learning technique was applied, female students outperformed male students. However, males outperformed females when using a competitive or individual learning technique.

Chief Examiner's Report (2016-2019) identified that electromagnetism questions are a major area where students often avoid or fail to answer in examinations. This failure has been linked to a poor method of teaching and abstract nature of the area. For a quite long time, Traditional Teaching Methods have been practiced in many classrooms in Zamfara State and Nigeria. This approach is teacher centered with the teacher dominating the class activities and not taking into account the students backgrounds and experiences. It cripples students' creativity and hides their skills. Based on this situation, the

researchers conducted the study to find out effects of J4IS on performance in concept of electromagnetism among secondary school physics students in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effects of J4IS on performance in concept of electromagnetism among secondary schools physics students in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara State. The specific objectives are to examine;

1. The mean difference in the academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis.
2. Difference in meexamineran academic performance of male and female students taught concept electromagnetism using J4IS in Gusau metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the research study.

1. What is the mean academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis?
2. What is the mean academic performance of male and female students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS in Gusau metropolis?

Research Hypothesis

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested in the course of this study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. **H₀₁**: there is no significant difference the mean academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis.
2. **H₀₂**: there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS in Gusau metropolis.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design was adopted. Students were exposed to J4IS on concept of electromagnetism. The population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school Students of Gusau L.G.A. which is 47,575 among which, 24,169 male and 23,406 female students from all the 29 Government Senior Secondary Schools Students under Gusau, Zamfara State. The schools were stratified into two that is male and female schools, out of each strata two schools were randomly selected making four schools. The sample size of 105 from the 4 sampled schools was used for the study as in accordance to Research Advisor (2006). Physics Performance Test (PPT) was developed as instrument for data collection. The research instrument was validated by 3 experts, 2 from Physics department and 1 from test and measurement in Federal University Gusau. The reliability of the instrument was determined using test retest method and a reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) which was considered reliable for the study. The study lasted for four weeks. Data for the research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while the formulated null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using T-test. Normalize mean gain was used to determine the strength of effectiveness of the strategy (J4IS).

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the mean academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis?

Table 2: Mean scores of students' performance in Control and Experimental Group

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Gain	Normalize Mean Gain
Control	105	42.36	10.883	30.21	52.4%
Experimental	105	72.57	11.365		

Source: Field work, (2022)

Table 2 shows that the mean scores in control group was 42.36 and the mean scores in experimental was 72.57. It was revealed that there was an improvement in the academic performance of the students when exposed J4IS since normalize mean gain above average. That is the mean gain (30.21) is 52.4% of the expected mean gain.

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference in the performance of students in control and experimental group when taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS.

Table 3: T-test analysis on students' performance in control and experimental group

Group	N	Mean	Df	T	Sig.
Control	105	42.36	208	-19.67	.000
Experimental	105	72.57			

Source: Field work, (2022)

Table 3 shows that a t-value at -19.67 and p-value (0.00) which is less than α (0.05) level of significance. Therefore, H₀₁ is rejected meaning there is significant difference between the performance of students in control and experimental group.0

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in mean academic performance of male and female students taught concept of electromagnetism with J4IS.

Table 4: The mean scores of male and female students' performance taught using J4IS

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Male	72	72.7083	10.86075	0.4356
Female	33	72.2727	12.56800	

Source: Field work, (2022)

Table 4 indicates that the mean score of male students in J4IS was 72.7083 and that of their female counterparts was 72.2727 with their mean difference of 0.4356. This shows that both perform relatively well when exposed to J4IS.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students taught with J4IS

Table 5: T-test analysis on students' performance based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Df	T	Sig.
Male	72	72.7083	103	.181	.856
Female	33	72.2727			

Source: Field work, (2022)

Table 5 shows P-value (0.856) which is greater than α (0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis is retained meaning that there is no significant difference between the performance of male and female students when taught with J4CLS.

Discussion of the Findings

The Results in table 1 suggested that the differences between the means academic performance of control group and experimental group using J4IS were statistically significant. This is a clear indication that this kind of method of instruction when effectively adopted by teachers would have effects on students' performance in physics and electromagnetism in particular. J4IS was found to record high academic mean scores and by implication very effective strategy. This finding is in line with that of Gök and Sylay (2010) who asserted that cooperative group problem solving is utilized because it is useful for sharing problem-solving techniques among groups and is an excellent way to teach complicated skills. It also simplifies complex problems.

More so, the results in table 3 indicated that there was no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of students based on gender that was taught electromagnetism using Jigsaw IV Instructional Strategy. This is in contrary with the findings of Okoro (2011), who opined that the instructional method used in classroom influences performance of students

based on gender in science. This implies J4IS does not discriminate against gender but rather provides opportunities for every student in their quest to improve in physics concepts such as electromagnetism.

Conclusion

It has been observed that, use of an appropriate J4IS in teaching concept of electromagnetism in Physics adequately improves students' performance in schools. And that J4IS is generally, gender friendly as the findings of this study show.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Physics teachers should be encouraged and well trained to employ J4IS in their physics classrooms to improve students' performances irrespective of school type and gender category.
2. The curriculum planners should incorporate J4IS in physics curriculum of senior secondary schools for effective teaching and learning.

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